

Disruptive Behavior In The Classroom: Recommendations For An Increasing Problem

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Abstract

Disruptive behavior in the classroom is a worldwide phenomenon. Scholars, researchers, and members of the school community share their concerns about it. This article investigates the concept, causes, effects, and possible recommendations to improve the learning and teaching experience in our schools. The review of the literature shows several findings to take into consideration: (1) Disruptive behavior must be identified as soon as possible to prevent its development and carry out needed interventions; (2) The most effective action model requires the coordination among all the subjects involved: students, parents, teachers, counselors, and mental health professionals; (3) Whatever action taken must be under the guiding educational principle of serving the best interest of students; (4) An adequate approach of this problematic will result in a positive, welcoming, and engaging classroom experience. Further research on the steady increase of classroom disruptions; early interventions, and time-consuming strategies on disruptors are needed to make the classroom experience effective and enjoyable for both learners and educators.

Keywords

Disruptive behavior; anti-social behavior; aggressive behavior; learning; teaching; school climate

1. INTRODUCTION

Disruptive behavior is becoming an issue in our schools creating many problems in the classroom: students' frustration, disengagement, and lack of motivation; teachers' burnout, dissatisfaction, and attrition; worsening of classroom learning atmosphere and relationships; lower academic achievement; loss of instructional time; and worsening of school and classroom culture and morale. As a consequence, students, teachers, parents, and communities are expressing their concerns. Disruptive behavior consumes large amount of time that should be allocated to instruction. Considering this scenario, it is essential to call for the attention of all members of the educational community to find solutions so that our learners enjoy their learning experience in a welcoming, caring, peaceful, and effective classroom. How can we prevent and minimize disruptive behavior in our classrooms? What are the causes of this disruptive behavior? Once the disruption occurs, what should be the mechanisms and protocols to be applied? The goal of this article is to understand these behaviors and provide solutions and recommendations so that instructors and learners can benefit from welcoming, peaceful, positive, and effective classrooms and schools.

2. DISRUPTIVE BEHAVIOR

In this section we tackle the concept of disruptive behavior, types, effects, causes, and studies.

2.1. CONCEPT

Akers (2010) describes disruptive behavior as repeated or continuous actions and deeds by students that become obstacles for instructors to teach and students to learn. These actions and deeds do not serve the best interests of learners, which should be the guiding principle to consider when making decisions in a school setting (Hansen, 2001; Hostetler, 1997).

According to that, educators and administrators must create a school culture where there is tolerance zero for those behaviors, sending a clear message: classrooms are places to learn and teach in a welcoming, peaceful, safe, and positive environment (Shernoff, 2013; Sugai et al., 2002).

2.2. TYPES

What are specifically these behaviors that create disruption in the classroom preventing other students from learning and teachers from delivering their lessons? There are many types of disruptive classroom behavior. Some examples include: arriving late, engaging in conversations unrelated to the lesson, talking out of turn, being out of one's seat without permission, inadequate use of technology, sleeping, working on something different from the class's subject, inappropriate language, being argumentative and/or confrontational, etc. Schools have students' handbooks where discipline and code of conduct are explained, with a clear description of rules and sanctions applicable if necessary. It is guaranteed due process (Buss, 1970) when the behavior of any student becomes disruptive and requires the application of disciplinary measures, included suspensions and expulsions.

2.3. CAUSES

What can be the reasons for disruptive classroom behavior? What can be the causes of a student to continuously and repeatedly act in an antisocial and disruptive way? Ghazi et al., (2013) mention 13 causes of disruptive behavior in secondary schools in Pakistan: inconsistent parenting; uncaring parents; overprotective parents; bad influences of a local community; poverty; poor quality teaching; teachers' negative attitude; repeating change in subject teacher; lack of teacher's motivation; repeating the same class; load shedding and lack of alternative; classroom poor conditions; and students' psych-problems. Bru (20026) adds three more factors of disruptive behavior in Norwegian schools: perceived low cognitive competence; perceived low relevance of school work, and the belief that norm-breaking behavior increases peer-approval. Banks (2020) adds 10 other causes of disruptive behavior in American schools: needs not being met; medical issues; student-teacher relationship issues; need of attention; power needs; lack of confidence and skills; curriculum adaptation problem; classroom environment; defiant attitude; and lack of consistency by leadership. Four more factors are mentioned by different scholars: rare early intervention (before 8 years old) (McNeil et al., 1999; Walker et al., 2003); lack of ethical values and principles (Gini et al., 2014; Paciello et al., 2017); soft on consequences discipline (Ullman, 2016); lack of administrative support (Buck, 2023; 2024). Therefore, we can see a multifactorial disruptive behavior system. In the next section, we are going to tackle the effects of these disruptive behaviors in the learning community.

2.4. EFFECTS

There is a common agreement among researchers (Douglas et al., 2016; Liaupsin et al., 2008) on the fact that disruptive behavior in the classroom brings negative effects to students, teachers, and school communities. Below, we refer to a series of effects of disruptive

behavior in the classroom:

1. Loss of instructional time. A 2003 American Federation of Teachers Poll reported that 36 percent of teachers acknowledged that they lost between two to four or more hours of teaching per week as a consequence of disruptions in the classroom. In connection with this, a Pew Research Center Report from 2024, states that 80 percent of teachers admits the presence of classroom disruptions few times a week, while 58 percent declares that these disruptions happen every day. In another survey conducted by Emma White Research, which included interviews with more than 1,000 public educators from Delaware Public Schools from July 10th to July 15th of 2024, educators stated that they lost an average of 7-10 hours of instruction per month due to behavioral challenges.

2. Low academic achievement for the disruptive student and disrupted classmates. Disrupting the class impedes learners to be focused, attentive, and on task. Without attention, learning cannot happen (Kruschke, 2003; Posner, 2014). The repercussions of disruptive students go beyond the disruptor, since other learners get disrupted by that behavior. This produces interruptions, distractions, and off-tasks behaviors which ultimately lowers learners' academic achievement (McGee et al., 2015; Schiman and Schiman, 2025).

3. Decreased student engagement and motivation. Disruptions prevent learners from paying attention. Without attention cannot be engagement which produces a lack of students' motivation. Nakamura and Csikzentmihalyi (2003) suggest that in order to find meaning in any activity, people must get involved in those activities. Disruptions are obstacles to get involved and therefore, to get engaged and motivated by such activities.

4. Prevents a welcoming, safe, and learning-based environment. Disruptive behavior jeopardizes the warmth and harmony that should be present in the classroom. Instead of being a welcoming, inviting, and learning-based environment, the classroom becomes an unsafe place where conflicts, confrontations, and aggressive behaviors may happen (Goldstein et al., 2008).

5. Anxiety for students and teachers. Anxiety is one of the most common issues in education. According to the American Academy of Pediatrics incidence of anxiety has increased over the past 10 years and affects up to 30 percent of adolescents. Disruptive behaviors in the classroom and anxiety in students and teacher are correlated (Bubier and Drabick, 2009; Forehand et al., 2013).

6. Teachers' stress and frustration. Student behavior is one of the leading causes for teachers' attrition (Kersaint et al., 2007). In this sense, George et al., (1995) found that more than three teachers out of ten would leave the profession due to the working conditions with students with emotional and behavioral disorders. Smith and Smith (2006) show a direct correlation between classroom disruptions and higher teachers' stress and burnout.

2.5. STUDIES

Kellam et al. (1994) conducted a longitudinal study with 1000 students in first grade. Researchers followed these students' classrooms until middle school creating two categories: orderly classrooms and chaotic classrooms. Findings showed how the students who started in their first grade with an aggressive behavior (as rated by their teachers) but attended orderly classrooms, had odds of 3:1 in favor of being highly aggressive. On the other hand, students who attended chaotic classrooms had odds of 59:1 to be highly aggressive in middle school. Eyberg et al., (2008) reviews the literature from 1996 to 2007 in which 16 evidence-based psychosocial treatments (EBTs) for children and adolescents with disruptive behavior are analyzed. Among these 16 EBTs, 15 met the requisites to be considered probably efficacious

treatments and one of them met requisites for a well-established treatment. These scholars' review recommends support for parent-training, child training, and teacher-training.

Epstein et al., (2015) conducted a meta-analysis on 28 studies regarding effectiveness of psychosocial interventions with children with disruptive behaviors. The analysis found that those interventions with a parent component, either alone or in conjunction with other components were more effective.

3. DISCUSSION

Disruptive behavior is a serious problem that happens too often in our schools. Its consequences are damaging for students, teachers, and school communities. Given the increasing frequency and effects of this phenomenon, and based upon the review carried out, we point out a series of recommendations that can be effective in providing better learning, teaching, academic, and working conditions for the individuals part of schools' communities:

- (1) Early interventions. McNeil et al., 1999 mention two psychiatric diagnoses as the main causes of disruptive behavior in classrooms: oppositional defiant disorder and conduct disorder. According to these scholars it is crucial to diagnose and treat these conditions as soon as possible, ideally by the age of eight. However, the reality is quite different: public schools often conclude a diagnosis on students' emotional or behavioral problems late in their school career, when those conducts became a habit and more difficult to treat. Therefore, when disruptive behaviors happen in a repetitive and consistent manner it is the moment to consider the possibility to refer them to special education services, where school therapists and professionals can design psychosocial interventional plans tailored to the needs of each student (Walker et al., (2003). Thus, an early identification, referral, and intervention of students with behavioral and emotional conditions may prevent the development of chronic and consistent disruptive conducts.
- (2) Clarifying expectations, with clear and consistent classroom rules and school policies. Each school has a series of prerogatives regarding discipline and rules of conduct. Teachers need to make sure that everybody in the classroom knows the expectations, rules and consequences applicable. This knowledge can be a deterrent for disruptive behaviors and a positive factor in obtaining a welcoming and effective learning environment (Payne et al., 2005).
- (3) Orderliness in the classroom. Neatness and tidiness; structured classroom routines; calm, quiet, and disarray-free environment are elements that help in having an absence of chaos in the classroom. Learning cannot be possible without attention (Kruschke, 2003), and chaos fosters a lack of attention. Therefore, orderly classrooms are obstacles for disruptive behaviors to develop (Kellam et al., 1994).
- (4) Effective classroom management. Many books and publications have been written on classroom management. The common denominator of these publications is that most of them are focused on giving teachers strategies to manage their classrooms. The type of student present in a particular classroom is an important factor in managing the classroom effectively (Marzano and Marzano, 2003). It is easy to manage the classroom when the students are hard-working, respectful, kind, and follow the rules. However, some students go to their classrooms with the purpose to continuously and consistently disrupt the learning environment. For these students, most of the strategies and actions suggested regarding classroom management publications are not going to work because these students might have an emotional or behavioral

conduct disorder. Next, we recommend a series of actions that can be effective in keeping a positive, welcoming, and inviting learning atmosphere:

- a. Being extra-firm the first days of school to set the tone for high behavioral and academic expectations.
 - b. When disruptive behavior occurs, respond immediately and consistently (Freiberg, 1983), avoiding patterns of disruption to flourish.
 - c. In the classroom, tolerance zero for disruptions (Ullman, 2016). Classrooms should be centers of learning and teaching, welcoming and inviting places to grow, both personally and academically. Keeping a healthy learning and teaching environment will help setting up the appropriate classroom culture.
 - d. Application of discipline and code of conduct of the school. Schools have a discipline and code of conduct system in place to be applied if necessary. Whenever any breach of conduct happens, consequences must follow. Teachers must report these infractions so that the disciplinary code is followed in the classroom. Suspensions and expulsions are part of schools' disciplinary system.
 - e. Change of activities often. Learners need to be challenged and kept busy. A working atmosphere will help learners be focused on work and learning.
- (5) Counseling office coordination. School counselors help students with academics, career options, and socio-emotional development. They represent a key factor in learners' success. An essential part of that success, it is that there must be a coordination effort to unite forces with teachers, parents, and administrators to provide the best help possible to students. Regarding disruptive students, we point out some actions that can help the school community:
- a. Avoiding following one another. In planning students' schedule, counselors must make sure disruptive students are not placed in the same classroom. Disruptive students have the tendency to follow one another, which in the classroom is going to be a source of chaos. Instead, students who are prone to disrupt the class, must be placed in a learning atmosphere where hard work, attention, eagerness to learn, and mutual respect are the habitual behaviors. A disruptor can be positively influenced by an environment where disruptions don't occur and learners support each other to thrive and keep learning (Bandura, 1977).
 - b. Separation of disruptors. If disruptive students are in the same classroom, counselors must separate them. Keeping these students in the same group will represent a source of frustration for the students who want to learn, considering the loss of instructional time due to disruptive behaviors. This idea of grouping students according to their aptitudes and attitudes is common in schools following the model of honor system (Schwartz et al., 2012). In education, it is considered a moral imperative for the profession to serve the best interest of the students (Shapiro and Stefkovich, 2016). In this sense, some students should not take away the learning process of students who want to learn (Erickson, 1976).
 - c. Conducting counselor-led psychosocial interventions with students, parents, therapists, and teachers. Counselors can coordinate sessions with disruptive students to be taught social, emotional, behavioral, and learning habits. These sessions can be one on one with the counselor, or in groups with other students, parents, teachers, and other professionals (Eyberg et al., 2008).
- (6) Chronically disruptive students should not be in a general classroom setting. These students who interfere with the learning process of others may need extra-services to

help them succeed in school. These services may be rendered by alternative classroom settings with behavior modification programs which provide learning and social strategies tailored for disruptive students' needs (Ferrera, 1993; Glass, 1995). These environments are characterized by a small teacher-student ratio which benefits the process to get these students ready to come back to a regular classroom.

- (7) Hiring more mental health professionals and teaching assistants. Due to the increasing number of disruptive behaviors in our schools, there is a push for more mental health professionals to better serve school communities (Sohn, 2024). In this sense, there are services already available at schools. Some of these services are provided by special education professionals who assess, develop, and plan strategies to help students with social and emotional conduct disorders as a result of their special education needs (Hopman et al., 2018). Also, it is recommended to hire more teacher assistants to help in classes where disruptive behaviors happen more often.
- (8) Smaller class sizes. Smaller classes are generally accepted as more adequate to create a welcoming and positive learning environment, since having less students allows teachers to dedicate more attention to each student. Therefore, this helps in managing behavior more effectively. Also, having a smaller class size helps in reducing the student-teacher ratio, which is an important factor in improving students' achievement (Koc and Celik, 2015).
- (9) Better disciplinary support from administrators. Considering that student behavior is one of the leading causes of teachers' burnout and leaving (Lincoln, 2024; Ward, 2022), it is important to reiterate the correlation that some scholars (Buck, 2023, 2024; Ullman, 2016;) found between repetitive disruptive behavior and a lack of administrative support based upon a soft on consequences discipline approach by administrators. It does make sense: if students break the rules of the disciplinary code of conduct, the teacher reports the infraction to the administrators, and the administrators don't give consequences, or the consequences are soft or lenient, students' disruptive behavior will be reinforced. On the other hand, teachers feel frustrated: they report the breach of conduct, but no consequences or soft consequences follow that report. The recommendation is simple: administrators must support teachers by applying the disciplinary consequences approved by the school. Not doing so, creates frustration and a lack of reporting by teachers, who in the end, get burnout and more prone to leave the profession.
- (10) Working conditions and career rewards should encourage teachers to continue in their profession (Geiger and Pivovarova, 2018). Reducing antisocial and aggressive behaviors enhances teachers' quality of work. Bettering teachers' working conditions is a corollary of creating a school culture where disruptive behaviors find obstacles to flourish. This is a beneficial factor in teacher retention. A constant flow of teachers coming and going, does not help in creating firm pillars in the school community.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Schools across the world are centers devoted to help learners be ready for their professional and personal lives. The next generations of learners will become the next generations of doctors, teachers, electricians, artists, etc. The future of our society is in their hands. Thus, educators hold a crucial mission in which they need to maximize their time to shape and develop the young minds of our future. In that endeavor, disruptive behavior represents an obstacle to use the resources and capabilities of an educational system designed to serve the

school community. A series of conclusions are presented: (1) Disruptive behavior is a serious issue that affects our schools. This issue needs to be identified as soon as possible and tackled properly. (2) In order to act effectively on this issue, it is key to act in coordination among the different actors in the school community (students, parents, teachers, counselors, administrators, etc.) to provide the best recommendation to each case. (3) Recommendations must serve a guiding ethical principle in our educational context: any decision made, has to be in the best interest of students. Too often, the constant attention to the few disruptors, prevents the education of the many. (4). It is imperative to build a positive, welcoming, and encouraging school culture where all the members know and assimilate the importance of learning, and the respect and care for one another.

Further research is needed in some aspects mentioned in this article. To name a few: reasons of constant increase of disruptive behaviors in schools; lack of early interventions for disruptive students; different amount of attention regarding disruptive and non-disruptive students, etc.

We really hope that this article represents a step in the right direction so that we can, all together, serve better in the best interest of all students.

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